

EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND THEIR IMPORTANCE

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Abstract. *This article describes the basics of organizing the educational process based on artificial intelligence.*

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In order to expand the use of artificial intelligence technologies, to improve the system of digital data collection, storage and processing, a number of works are currently being carried out in our country to train qualified personnel in this field, to support scientific projects in this direction.

In February 2021, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev decided to create conditions for the development of artificial intelligence technologies. This was first manifested in education: a new faculty in the field of artificial intelligence was established in 4 prestigious higher education institutions. These universities are: Tashkent University of Information Technologies, National University of Uzbekistan, Samarkand State University, Technical Universities. It was introduced as an applied science in 15 universities. Also, the Scientific Research Institute of Artificial Intelligence Technologies was established under the Ministry of Digital Technologies. The only integrator of production and support of state information systems under the Ministry of Digital Technologies is UZINFOCOM. "Mukhlisa" voice system and "MyID" were developed with the help of this organization. More than 70 offices and organizations have more than 10 million users of the MyID system. An agreement was signed on the use of "Mukhlisa" voice assistant in BYD cars manufactured in Uzbekistan.

In turn, it is necessary to increase the number of qualified personnel to introduce artificial intelligence to science. After all, experts who are masters of their profession are the main factor in the penetration of artificial intelligence into all areas. Currently, in our republic, the specialty "Digital technologies and artificial intelligence" in this direction has been included in the nomenclature of scientific and scientific-pedagogical specialties of highly qualified personnel, and its passport has been created. A post-higher education institute for "Digital technologies and artificial intelligence" was opened at Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khorazmi and the Research Institute for the Development of Digital Technologies and Artificial Intelligence.

In the framework of supporting scientific and technical research and innovative developments in the field of artificial intelligence, the total cost is 15.1 billion. 9 projects with a duration of 2021-2024 are being implemented.

Intelligence is the ability to learn and solve problems. Artificial intelligence means simulating human intelligence with the help of machines. Including the ability to find solutions to problems, the ability to act rationally, the ability to think like or more than people.

The basic principles of artificial intelligence include thinking, knowledge, planning, learning and communication, perception, as well as the ability to move and manipulate objects,

artificial intelligence is the science and engineering of creating intelligent machines, especially intelligent computer programs.

In the modern world, artificial intelligence systems perform millions of actions in real time. They serve development by making optimal decisions based on necessary information in milliseconds. From self-driving cars to healthcare applications, everything is the result of intelligent systems created by programmers.

The main purpose or principle of operation of artificial intelligence is to enable electronic devices to perform intellectual tasks such as decision making, problem solving, perception, understanding and translating human communication in any language.

According to data, over the next three years, by 2025, more than 47% of learning management tools will be connected to artificial intelligence technology. In this strategy, the work to be carried out until 2030 is set as a goal.

The main reason (and many others) is learning through personalization, and choosing what to study is one of the biggest trends in education. Artificial intelligence takes into account the abilities of students and offers appropriate training programs. In this case, online learning platforms can adapt to the student's level of knowledge, learning speed and any other aspects. As a result, they are more interested in learning. In addition, AI-based solutions can analyze students' previous learning history, identify weaknesses and suggest the most suitable courses for improvement, and provide more opportunities for a personalized learning experience.

Intellect (Latin intellectus - sense, perception, understanding) or intelligence - the quality of the psyche consisting of the ability to adapt to new situations, learn and remember based on experience, and use one's own knowledge to understand and apply abstract concepts, manage the environment use.

Intelligence is the general ability to study and solve problems that combines all cognitive abilities of a person: feeling, perception, memory, representation, thinking, imagination.

Artificial intelligence is a special field of computer science, which deals with the creation of computer systems with the capabilities usually associated with the human mind: language understanding, teaching, discussion, problem solving, translation, and similar capabilities. Artificial intelligence (AI) allows computers to learn from their experiences, adapt to given parameters, and perform tasks previously only possible for humans. In many AI implementations—from computer chess players to unmanned vehicles—deep learning and natural language processing capabilities are critical. Thanks to these technologies, computers can be "trained" to perform certain tasks by processing large amounts of data and identifying patterns in them.

In the early 1980s, computational scientists Barr and Feigenbaum proposed the following definition of artificial intelligence (AI):

"Artificial intelligence is the field of computer science that deals with the development of intelligent computer systems, systems that have the capabilities we traditionally associate with the human mind and the ability to understand language, reason is to solve problems and be able to solve other problems".

Later, a number of algorithms and software systems began to be called artificial intelligence, the distinguishing feature of which is that they can solve certain problems in the same way that a person thinks about solving them.

The main characteristics of SI are the ability to understand language, learn, think and, most importantly, act.

SI is a complex of high-quality and rapidly developing relevant technologies and processes, such as: natural language text processing; machine learning; expert systems; virtual agents (chatbots and virtual assistants).

As of 2021, researchers have used the following classification of SI types:

Artificial Super Intelligence (SSI) is a hypothetical artificial intelligence that can not only replicate, but also surpass, the maximum capabilities of humans. Believers in SSI claim that it has the power to tap into a person's thoughts and emotions in order to bend them to their will. Here, for example: futuristic horror stories or the real future of artificial intelligence.

Also, hypothetically strong or general SI (Artificial General Intelligence, SUI) is one step lower than SSI in terms of rationality, and proponents of this type of SI are at least able to function in their beliefs.

Advantages of AI in education

The emergence of AI (artificial intelligence) in the classroom is not just a breakthrough, it raises fundamental questions about the current education system. The convergence of technology and teaching is not only changing the way students learn, but it is also generating a great deal of debate about the challenges and possibilities of its impact. It helps in the automatic assessment of the quality of knowledge in the assessment of educational issues and homework. Currently, in order to determine the level of knowledge of English language in our country, that is, in the CEFR exams, while reducing the human factor, they are evaluating the knowledge and skills of applicants with the help of bots, as a result, they are creating opportunities to quickly get the results of the exams.

1. Educational theories and approaches

Artificial intelligence is used in the educational process in accordance with the following educational theories:

- **Constructivism:** By providing students with opportunities for independent learning, AI promotes constructivist learning. For example, SI creates customized tasks and activities for students, providing an individual learning path based on their level of knowledge.
- **Behaviorism:** SI-based interactive learning resources and games can increase students' learning motivation with reward and repetition mechanisms by monitoring their behavior.
- **Cognitivism:** The ability of artificial intelligence to analyze large amounts of data and suggest the most appropriate learning paths for individual students supports the implementation of a cognitive approach to education.

2. Individualized teaching and differential approach

SI technologies create individualized learning plans by analyzing students' knowledge levels, learning styles and abilities. In this process, artificial intelligence-based learning algorithms help identify each student's strengths and weaknesses, offering personalized learning.

3. Data analysis and knowledge tracking

Artificial intelligence makes it possible to analyze and optimize the training process based on data. This data helps teachers see student achievement, success, and weaknesses. Through SI-based platforms, student learning can be monitored in real-time and educational resources can be modified accordingly.

4. Automation of the educational process

AI can be widely used in learning automation: for example, automatically checking tests, answering students' questions and providing them with tailored content. This allows teachers to focus more on the learning process and adapt to the individual needs of students.

5. Customized education and self-study

Educational resources created with SI provide personalized and flexible learning platforms for students to learn at their own time. For example, adaptive learning systems adjust content based on the level of knowledge of students and recommend a course of development.

6. Interactivity and immersive technologies

Educational resources based on artificial intelligence are interactive and provide an immersive environment, for example, providing students with hands-on experiences using virtual or augmented reality technologies. In this process, SI can monitor students' actions and provide flexible support in real time.

7. Support and tools for teachers

SI also provides useful opportunities for teachers, such as lesson planning, knowledge analysis and diagnosis, student monitoring and data summarization. With the help of SI, teachers can organize the teaching process more effectively.

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